

RI4C2
Research & Innovation
For Cities & Citizens

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Masterclass for Gender Equality in R&I

Conference

DELIVERABLE 3.4
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D3.4 Masterclass for Gender Equality in R&I

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I. Introduction

One of the European Commission's priority areas for the European Research Area is **Priority area 5 - Promoting Gender Equality and Fostering Inclusion, taking note of the Ljubljana declaration** as defined in the document [European Research Area \(ERA\) Policy Agenda 2021 - 2024](#). In particular, the European Commission makes it clear that "Gender Equality is a fundamental value of the EU and gender mainstreaming a key EU strategy". Here also, the European Campus of City Universities Alliance (EC2U) and the Research and Innovation for Cities and Citizens (RI4C2) Project are aligned with the European Commission as they both consider gender-related issues as a top priority for their Research and Innovation communities.

Thus, the Working Package 3 (WP3), "People Empowerment", led by the University of Coimbra (UC) and implemented by the Interdisciplinary Research Institute of the University of Coimbra (IIIUC), in cooperation with the RI4C2 Partners, has the main objectives of analysing and creating measures that reflect on careers in the Research and Innovation Areas of the EC2U Alliance. Thinking about the careers of Researchers and Innovators means considering the different spheres that make them up, such as ethical aspects, selection and recruitment, working conditions, the balance between family life and professional tasks, as well as **Gender Equality**.

The goal is to support the scientific community in developing a career capable of recognising and dignifying the various professions linked to science and innovation, as well as training, and alerting these professionals to the importance of gender issues in their daily tasks.

To fulfil these objectives, different actions and activities are being implemented, such as the recording of "**Masterclasses for Gender Equality in R&I**". These online masterclasses bring together the EC2U Alliance's and RI4C2 Project best practices and experts on Gender Equality.

The masterclasses are available online on the [EC2U YouTube official channel](#), as well as on the [EC2U Alliance website](#), so that this information is accessible to everyone inside and outside the Alliance's community.

II. Masterclass “Gender Equality and Inclusive Communication in Research & Innovation Activities”

A. Summary

Higher education institutions are in a strategic position to create and implement recommendations for Gender Equality putting into practice concrete measures to overcome obstacles and promote equality and diversity. Going beyond the focus on interpersonal actions there must be a strategic recognition of structural issues that create barriers to an equitable and inclusive environment that recognises and responds to the diversity of lived experiences and existing identities.

This Masterclass discusses Gender Equality and Inclusive Communication in Research and Innovation Activities addressing practical aspects that can contribute to improving everyday practice in teaching, supervising, mentoring, and researching.

B. Expert biography

This masterclass was presented by Rita Alcaire, who is an anthropologist, documentary filmmaker, and social science communicator working at the intersection of social sciences, media and arts. She is a postdoctoral researcher at the Centre for Social Studies at the University of Coimbra. She holds a PhD in Human Rights and a MA in Cultural Psychiatry. Her research interests lie in the study of gender and sexualities, mental health, and pop culture using the media as a privileged way to engage with them.

C. Links to recording

Available at:

- [EC2U Website](#)
- [EC2U Alliance Official YouTube Channel](#)

III. Masterclass “The Ethics of Gender Equality in Science and Research”

A. Summary

This Gender Equality Masterclass aims at addressing the topic of the gender gap in science through the ethics of research approach.

An overview of relevant data, current policies and best practices is carried out in order to provide an insight on one of the main contemporary challenges in research.

B. Expert biography

The speaker for this masterclass is Daniela Ovadia, an Italian science journalist, neuroscientist, and neuroethicist. She studied medicine and neuroscience at Università Statale in Milan, Italy, and neuroethics at the University of Pennsylvania in Philadelphia, US. She serves as the Co-director of the Neuroscience and Society Lab at the University of Pavia and is also the Scientific Director of Agenzia Zoe, an agency specialising in science journalism and writing.

Furthermore, she holds the position of professor in subjects such as “Ethics of Research and Responsible Research and Innovation” for doctoral students, “Neuroethics,” and “Communication of Neuroscience” for undergraduate students in Psychology at the University of Pavia in Italy.

C. Links to recording

Available at:

- [EC2U Website](#)
- [EC2U Alliance Official YouTube Channel](#)

IV. Masterclass “Fostering gender equality at the university through policy and practice”

A. Summary

Part 1 - The University of Poitiers equality task force

The first part of the masterclass presents some of the measures and actions recently introduced by the University to promote gender equality and diversity, and to combat discrimination. The description of this structurally unfinished and increasingly demanding task is also an opportunity to share experiences and reflect, not only on how to think about a policy of substantive equality, but also on the role of the university in the contemporary world.

Part 2 - The « Sciences en Mouvement d’Elles » project

The second part of the masterclass aims to highlight women’s career paths in research and entrepreneurship, and to address stereotypes and gender inequality in these fields. It provides an overview of the “Sciences En Mouvement d’Elles” project through the account of Albane Rozenholc, a PhD student at the University of Poitiers, who is involved in this initiative.

B. Experts’ biographies

The speaker in the first part of the masterclass is **Catherine Rannoux**. She is a Professor of French and stylistics at the University of Poitiers. In charge of the equality and diversity task force, she leads the gender equality and anti-discrimination policy at the University of Poitiers. She is also President of the select academic board, which is in charge of all matters related to teachers and researchers’ careers at the University of Poitiers.

The speaker in the second part of the masterclass is **Albane Rozenholc**. She is a PhD Student in Microbiology and Molecular biology at the University of Poitiers, School of Medicine and Pharmacy, in unit UMR 1070 “Pharmacology of Antimicrobial Agents”.

C. Links to recording

Available at:

- [EC2U Website](#)
- [EC2U Alliance Official YouTube Channel](#)

V. Concluding remarks

Considering that the Gender Equality component is one of the pillars of the RI4C2 project, training our teams in this area is essential for the accomplishment of our goals. For that reason, several team members participate in activities promoted by EC2U Alliance universities in order to improve their competences in this area. As an example, in the last couple of months, some colleagues have taken part in and collaborated with the [Gender@UC EEA Grants](#) activities.

VI. References

European Commission (2023). *European Research Area (ERA) Policy Agenda 2021 - 2024*. Available at https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-11/ec_rtd_era-policy-agenda-2021.pdf

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Alcaire, Rita (2023). *Gender Equality and Inclusive Communication in Research and Innovation activities (2023)*. Available at

Ovadia, Daniela (2023). *The ethics of Gender Equality in Science and Research*. Available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2gAiSkul7UQ>

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